

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL HEALTH STATISTICS; IMPLICATION FOR HEALTH EDUCATION AND PROMOTION

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the differences in health statistics of some selected developing and developed countries. Secondary data were sourced from various international sources such as World Fact book (2008), World Health Organization (2010) and UNICEF(2010). The variables of the study were HIV/AIDS prevalence and education statistics of Nigeria, Ghana Australia, USA countries formed the dependent. HIV/AIDS is not significant as a predictor of life expectancy in these countries as HIV/AIDS statistics of the five countries contributed 5.4% to life expectancy ($R=0.548$). However it is a predictor of life expectancy in Ghana and Nigeria, with a t-value of 2.975 and -3.090 respectively. Both were significant at 0.05 alpha levels. The t-value of all five countries shows that none was significant in the use of education as a predictor of life expectancy. It was recommended that Nigerian government should raise health expenditure to the agreed 15% of the budget and make more effort at increasing school enrollment at the primary and secondary levels. This must be followed with employment opportunities to raise the living standard of the people. This comprehensive approach to health status will increase life expectancy among Nigeria.

KEYWORDS; Health statistics, health indicators, developed developing countries, HIV/AIDS prevalence, the level of education

INTRODUCTION

Health and medical statistics incorporate a variety of data types. The most common statistics reported are vital (birth, death, marriage, divorce rates), morbidity (incidence of disease in a population) and mortality (the number of people who die of a certain disease compared with the total number of people). Other common statistical data reported are health care costs, the demographic distribution of disease based on geographic, ethnic, and gender variables, and data on the socioeconomic status and education of health care professionals. Okonjo-Iweala and Osafo-Kwaako (2007) described the relevance of statistics for effective health-care delivery in developing countries. According to the authors, the availability of statistics is crucial in the fight against poverty, and is a necessary starting point to quantify outcomes needed to monitor and measure progress towards the Millennium Development Goals.

Locating health statistics in developing countries like Ghana and Nigeria is usually more problematic than locating data in U K and USA. Resources, particularly in developing countries, may not be available to collect data as extensively or comprehensively as in the United States. Thus, the lack of reliable and good-quality statistics is a major obstacle in assessing changes in the indicators in many African countries. WHO (2008) asserts that the African countries with inadequate statistical capacity and measurement systems are the ones that suffer more from deadly diseases such as HIV/AIDS and malaria. The lack of health statistics ranges from poor systems for civil registration to poor data on immunization and child mortality rates. Data collecting efforts therefore vary considerably around the world and comparative data may not be available.

Very often, the health indicators in developed countries like Britain, USA, and Australia are used as reference point while discussing health indicators and statistics in developing countries like Nigeria, Ghana, and others. Looking through literatures there is a dearth of studies on comparative studies on the indicators on HIV / AIDS prevalence, Education and Health statistics between developed countries and developing countries (WHO, 2010, Shah, 2010). This could be due to the fact that researchers believed that the developed countries health statistics should form the bases for the aspiration of developing countries. Thus the differences in health statistics of the developed countries against the developing countries are often taken as mere difference, which are only needed

in policy making and decision-making. This discrepancy in opinion forms the rationale for study. While it will be a goose-chase to discuss or study the multiple variables of global statistics in a single study, however an attempt was made to study a few of the health indicators in this study. This study examined the differences in health statistics of some selected developing and developed countries. HIV/AIDS prevalence and the level of education of the-citizenry or level of literacy in selected countries; Australia, Britain, USA, Ghana and Nigeria are examined.

Research Question:

Will the prevalence of HIV/AIDS be a determinant of the health status of some selected counties (Australia, Britain, Ghana, Nigeria and the United States of America)

Will the level of educational development through children enrollment in schools be a determinant of the health status of some selected parts of the global (Australia, Britain, Ghana, Nigeria and the United States of America).

Hypothesis

Two-variable based hypotheses derived from the research questions were used.

HIV / AIDS prevalence will not be a significant determinant of Health status as indicated by life expectancy of some selected counties part of the world (Australia, Britain, Ghana, Nigeria and United States of America).

Education development through children enrollment in schools will not be a significant determinant of the Health Status as indicated by life expectancy of some selected countries of the world, (Australia, United Kingdom, Ghana, Nigeria, and United States of America).

Literature review

Despite incredible improvements in health since 1950, there are still a number of challenges, as depicted by the following global statistics; One billion people lack access to health care systems, 36 million deaths each year are caused by non communicable diseases, such as cardiovascular disease, cancer, diabetes and chronic lung diseases (Gibson et. al, 2010). Over 7.5 million children under the age of 5 die from malnutrition and mostly preventable diseases, each year In 2008, some 6.7 million people died of infectious diseases alone, far more than the number killed in the natural or man-made catastrophes that make headlines (WHO,2010). AIDS/HIV has spread rapidly. UNAIDS estimates for 2008 that there were roughly: million living with HIV, 2.7 million new infections of HIV, 2 million deaths from AIDS, Tuberculosis kills 1.7 million people each year, with 9.4 million new cases a year. , 1.6 million People still die from pneumococcal diseases every year, making it the number one vaccine-preventable cause of death worldwide., Malaria causes some 225 million acute illnesses and over 780,000 deaths, annually (Source WHO fact sheet (2010)

Although the statistics above make for grim reading, an important underlying cause of all these deaths is poverty. The World Health Organization (WHO) and other international organisations repeatedly point out that many of these diseases are related to poverty. According to WHO (2010)the poorest of the poor, around the world, have the worst health, often disadvantaged by historical exploitation and persistent inequity in global institutions of power and policy-making.

A look at the disposition of the rich countries of the world shows that low socioeconomic position means poor education, lack of amenities, unemployment and job insecurity, poor working conditions, and unsafe neighborhoods, with their consequent impact on family life. This is in addition to the considerable burden of material deprivation and vulnerability to natural disasters. So these dimensions of social disadvantage have implication for health.

A brief discourse on the health of this selected countries succinctly brings out the fact that the key determinants of health of individuals and populations are the circumstances in which people are born, grow, live, work and age, and those circumstances are affected by the social and economic environment.

Africa and Health Care

The health care systems inherited by most African states (Nigeria and Ghana inclusive) after the colonial era were unevenly weighted toward privileged elites and urban centers (Gibson et. al, 2010). In the 1960s and

1970s, substantial progress most African governments endeavored to redress the inequalities of the colonial era. As African governments became clients of the World Bank and IMF, they forfeited control over their domestic spending priorities. The loan conditions of these institutions according to (Shah, 2011b) forced contraction in government spending on health and other social services resulting in intensified poverty and increased the vulnerability of African populations to the spread of diseases and to other health problems. Declining living conditions and reduced access to basic services have led to decreased health status. In Africa today, almost half of the population lacks access to safe water and adequate sanitation services. As immune systems have become weakened, the susceptibility of Africa's people to infectious diseases has greatly increased.

The US and Health Care

The US is the only industrialized country that does not have universal health care for all its citizens (Read, 2009). It has programs for the elderly, military service families, the disabled, children and some poor through programs such as Medicare and Medicaid. With the worsening global financial crisis hitting America hard, more are likely to lose medical insurance which is often associated with a job. US spends the most per person (in the world) on health care, yet does not get the best for all that money US has not seen health as a human right, but as a privilege (Pears, 2008).. However, President Barack Obama has tried to challenge this view, with proposed reforms to provide universal health care through health insurance for all. This has been met with wrath from the right wing, The US through the federal law provide public access to emergency services, regardless of ability to pay. However, many who cannot afford regular health care either use emergency services for treatment, or let otherwise preventable conditions get worse, requiring emergency treatment.

The *New York Times* reports that life expectancy disparities in US are mirroring the widening income inequality in recent decades (Reid, 2009). Other health issues that are pronounced in the US, include; obesity, high cost of medical drugs, lack of access for large numbers of people.

Britain's National Health Service

Britain has had a national health service (NHS) since the late 1940s. While tax-funded and government run, it provides access to all citizens and is mostly free at point of use. The British system includes free primary care paying doctors and running hospitals through decentralized trusts (Shah, 2011b.)Almost all treatment is free. For working age citizens, prescriptions are obtained with a flat fee (with pharmacists often telling patients if the same drug is cheaper over the counter than through prescription). Dentist and optician visits typically have some fee associated with them, with dentistry having been increasingly privatized for many, many years.

According to Shah (2011a) there is a parallel private health option but is used by a small percentage of the population (usually the wealthy, by definition). Despite some on-going issues (as with all systems), the service provides universal care with generally low wait times, even as it faces budgetary constraints and changing social habits for which the health system wasn't necessarily designed (just two examples being increasingly excessive alcohol consumption and obesity).

HIV/AIDS Prevalence

AIDS, a disease caused by Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) is a global pandemic disease of all Nation's concern, Damilola (2004) citing April 2001 African Heads of State Summit stated that in less than 20 years, a staggering 11,6 million Africans have died from HIV/ AIDS, almost three million of whom are within the active age group. In addition, more than 90% of existing AIDS orphans worldwide live in Africa and Africa has 80% of all AIDS related deaths and 70% of all new HIV infections. The International Development Magazine (2002) reported that AIDS has generated a lot of controversy resulting in the development of a wide propaganda machine, The magazine stated further that there is nowhere in the world that enlightenment and awareness campaigns against AIDS have not reached. Every day, about 15,000 people throughout the world became infected with the HIV virus. Uwakwe (1999) stated further that about 60% of these are women and men between the 15 - 24 years of age. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) (2005) stated that roughly 500,000 children younger than 15 years died of the HIV/AIDS in 2005 alone and children accounted for 13% of new infection in 2004, The organization reported further that in 2006, 2.6 million adults and 380,000 children under 15 years died of AIDS, and as November 2005, young women accounted for nearly 50% of the more than 37 million people living with HIV world wide and 60% in sub-Sahara Africa. Joint UNAIDS/WHO (2007) reported that as of November 2007, 68% of all people who are HIV positive live in developing region where 76% of all AIDS

deaths in 2007 occurred. Furthermore, of the number of people living with HIV, 7.5% are young people. AIDS Treatment News (2002) averred that a person who has full-blown AIDS may exhibit any of the following symptoms: prolonged diarrhea, white coating in the mouth or throat, persistent fever, loss of weight, enlargement of glands and brain tumor. Consequently, there will be a reduction in such a person's productivity in the workplace _ because of constant absenteeism due to AIDS - specific illness (Damilola, 2004).

Effect of HIV/AIDS Pandemic on Nation's Economy

Damilola (2004) citing The International Development Magazine (2002) reported that the economical active age group of 15- 45 years old population of the developing world is severely hit with HIV/AIDS infection. Consequently, the morbidity and mortality arising from HIV/AIDS infections will manifest in skill shortage and low human capacity development. This will reduce productivity as labour reduces or weakened, low investment incentive and strained government budget. Shokunbi (2002) stated that morbidity and mortality due to HIV/AIDS is drastically reducing the size of the nations spending in health. U. N Security Council (2001) acknowledged HI V / AIDS as global security risk as well as a human security issue.

Reducing the Prevalence of AIDS

Nwimo (2008) suggested that efforts have to be addressed to promote consistent and adequate condom use and anonymous free condom distribution should be implemented. He also stated that a model of AIDS prevention for young adult in developing countries needs to be addressed the ability to negotiate safe sex, peer norms, gender norms and beliefs about efficacy of using condom. He further stated that intervention programmes aimed at less educated and unemployed young people should be part of effective HIV-prevention strategy. To control the spread of HIV/AIDS, Okoye and Nwokolo (2008) suggested that there should be free HIV/AIDS tests in homes, schools and other public places like hospital and industries. This will expose positive persons and counseled on the use of antiviral drugs to prolong their life and guide against spread. Abdu (2006) stated that sex education be a compulsory course for all students at all levels of education.

Education

Education is one of the instrument with which national development would be measured. In most countries, efforts are made through research to determine the level of literacy. In others, the number of universities is used to determine the level of development. Hence, quality in education is a multi-dimensional concept which should embrace' all functions and activities: teaching and academic programmes, research and scholarship, staffing, students, buildings, facilities, equipment, services to the community and academic environment (UNESCO 1998). In Nigeria for example, Education has evolved a long period of time, with a series of policy changes. Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (2003) further stated that on October 1999 the Universal Basic Education was launched, making it compulsory for every child to be educated free tuition up to the secondary school level in an effort to meet Nigerian's manpower requirement for national development.

In Ghana, youth (15-24 years) literacy rate was 80% between 2003-2007. Primary school enrollment between 2003 - 2008 was 98%, while secondary enrollment between 2003 - 2008 was 45%. In United Kingdom, primary school enrolment in 2003 - 2008 was 98% while in primary school enrollment between 2003 - 2008 in United State of America was 98% and secondary school enrollment ratio between 2003 - 2008, was 89% (UNICEF, 2010).

Most issue in education with reference to development is usually based on finance and human resources. Maduewesi (2005) stated the finance and human resources are more readily available on a global scale. According to her, by finance, reference is being made to public investment in education. Human resources, refers to such indicators is learner enrollment, teacher quality, as well as learner/teacher ratio. Maduewesi (2005) cited UNISCO (2002) in a graph demonstrated that about two and half ($2\frac{1}{2}$) to about twenty- five (25) billion US Dollar were spent to achieve about 30 millions school enrollment while East Asia in the same period spent about $2\frac{1}{2}$ -2 5billion US Dollar to achieve about $42\frac{1}{2}$ million school enrolment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study employed secondary data sourced from various international sources such as CIA World Fact book 2008, World Health Organization (2010), UNICEF (2010) among others. Data on HIV/AIDS were converted to percentages ages based on the country's population. This is to make it acceptable for use along with others presented in percentages. Education data were presented in ratios per thousand of the population for all countries

and used as such.

The variables of the study were HIV/ AIDS and Education Statistics of Nigeria, Australia, USA., United Kingdom and Ghana. This forms the independent variables while the life expectancy of Nigeria Australia, USA United Kingdom and Ghana formed the dependent.

Empirical Specification

In order to test hypothesis and answer research questions, an empirical equation were specified for each hypothesis. The multiple regression analysis was used to analyse the data. The independent variables for each sub hypothesis were:-

$$y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 + x_3) \dots\dots\dots + b_n X_n$$

Where

y is the dependent variable

a is the point of intercept of the y axis

b is the coefficient attached to both relevant independent variable $X_1 X_2 X_3 \dots X_n$ are explanatory variables.

Analysis of data

The SPSS version was used to analyze the data.

Ho..... 1

Sub - equation 1

HS = f (HIV statistics in Australia, U.K, USA, Nigeria and Ghana) --- (1) life expectancy.

Ho..... 2

Sub - hypothesis - 2

HS f (Education indicators in Australia, U.K, USA, Nigeria and Ghana) --- (1) Life expectancy

HS - Means, Health status

Findings

Table 1: Multiple regression analysis of HIV/AIDS statistics in Australia, United Kingdom, United States of America, Ghana and Nigeria as predictors of life expectancy in these countries

Table 1 a: Descriptive Statistics of means and standard deviation of HI VI AIDS statistics in the countries under study

HIV I AIDS Statistics	Mean	Std Dev	N
Life Expectancy	73.33	9.597	15
Australia	0.05480	0.0775	15
U.K	0.06921	0.09726	15
U.S .A	0.060164-	0.08251	15
Ghana	0.392547	0.5446	15
Nigeria	0.819467	1.0524	15

Table 1 b: ANOVA summary of multiple regressions of HIV/AIDS statistics in Australia, U K, USA, Ghana, and Nigeria.

Model	Sum of Square	Dr	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	706.190	5	141.238	2.180	0.146
Residual	583.143	9	64.794		
Total	1289.333	14			

(a) Predictors (constant) Nigeria, U.K, USA, Ghana, Australia.
R = .740

(b) Dependent Variable Life Expectancy
Rf= .548
Adjusted R2 = .296

Table 1c: Coefficients of multiple regressions of HIV/AIDS statistics in Australia, U.K, USA, Ghana, and Nigeria

Dependent Variable:

Table la, b & c were the regression analysis for HIV/AIDS as predictor of life expectancy. The statistics on

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Std Coefficient	t	Sig	95% Cost Interval For B	
	B	Std error	Beta			Bound	Bound
Constant	73.564	2.799		26.280	.000	67.232	79.897
Australia	93.427	82.973	.755	1.126	.289	-94.271	281.126
U.K.U.K.	-30.018	48.245	-.304	-.622	.549	-139.156	79.121
USA	-23.238	45.812	-.200	-.530	.609	-122.348	75.873
Ghana	27.654	9.295	1.570	2.975	.016	6.627	48.679
Nigeria	-16.754	5.423	-1.837	-3.090	.013	-29.021	-4.487

HIV/AIDS show that Nigeria with a mean of 0.8194 and standard deviation of 1.0524 has the highest level of HIV / AIDS infected. Australia with mean of 0.054 and a standard deviation of 0.0775 has the least level of HIV AIDS prevalence, ANOVA summary revealed the F value to be 2.180 at a df of 5:9 at 0.05 alpha level which was significant. HIV/ AIDS statistics of the five countries put together contributed 5.4% to life expectancy in these countries. (R=0.548). These figures show that HIV/AIDS is not significant as a predictor of life expectancy in these countries. A further analysis showed a t-value of 2.975 for Ghana and -3.090 for Nigeria. Both figures were significant at 0.05 alpha level; but not for Australia, United Kingdom and United States of America. The t-value for Ghana and Nigeria showed that HIV/AIDS Statistics was a predictor of life expectancy in Nigeria and Ghana.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis of Education as predictor of life expectancy in these countries.

Table 2a: Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation of Education indicators in Australia, U .K, Ghana and Nigeria.

	Mean	Std Dev	N
Life Expectancy	0.87667	10.16905	15
Australia	70.9867	52.8406	15
U.K	67.0267	46.2695	15
U.S.A	62.4800	41.6684	15
Ghana	41.0733	32.8558	15
Nigeria	33.6667	31.6106	15

Table 2b: ANOVA summary of multiple regression of Education indicators in Australia, U.K, USA, Ghana and Nigeria.

Model	Sum of Square	Df	Mean Square	F	Sign
Regression	332.022	5	66.404		
Residual	1115.711	9	123.968	0.536	0.745
Total	1447.733	14			

a) Predictors: (Education indicators in Australia, Nigeria, USA, Ghana and U.K) .
 . (b) Dependent Variable: Life Expectancy
 R=479
 R2 = 29
 Adjusted R²=-199

Table 2c: Co-efficient of multiple regression analysis of Education as a predictor of life expectancy

Model	Unstandardize Coefficient		Std Coefficient	95% Cost Interval For B			
	B	Std error	Beta	t	Sig	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Constant	76.591	5.718		13.395	.00		
Australia	.125	.166	.649	.753	.471		
U.K	.249	.387	1.134	.644	.535		
USA	-.520	.441	-2.131	-1.180	.268		
Ghana	-.170	.430	.550	-.396	.701		
Nigeria	.243	.414	.755	.586	.572		

Dependent Variable: Life Expectancy.

Table 2a, b and c spelt out the multiple regressions of education indicators as a predictor of life expectancy in Australia, United Kingdom and the United States of America, Ghana and Nigeria. The education indicators reveal a mean of 70.9867 and standard deviation of 52.8406 for Australia as the country with the highest level of school enrollment among the five countries. Nigeria with a mean of 33.6667, and a standard deviation of 31.61 06 has the least member among the five countries in education.

An ANOVA summary showed on an f-value of 0.536 at degree of freedom of 5:9 and alpha level of 0.05. This was considered not significant as a predictor of life expectancy in the countries under study. With an R^2 of 0.229 this shows that education contributed 2% to life expectancy in the five countries. A t-value analysis shows that none of the countries has significant t-value. Therefore education indicator was not a predictor of life expectancy in the five countries under study.

DISCUSSION

This study has shown that prevalence of HIV/AIDS do not have the same effect in every country. While HIV/AIDS infection could be used as a predictor in Ghana and Nigeria (developing countries) with -3.090 and 2.975 t-value respectively, which was considered significant in predicting life expectancy, it was not the same for Australia, United Kingdom and United states of America (developed countries). This finding supports that of Davidamuk (2008) who remarked that current social development and health indicators from international and African institutions shows that over eight (8) million African lives are lost annually to preventable, treatable and manageable health conditions and diseases mainly – child mortality, maternal mortality, HIV/AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis.

This study has shown also that level of education in a country is not predictive of life expectancy in the five countries with an F-value of 0.536 at a df of 5:9 and alpha level of 0.05. This was considered insignificant using education indicator as predictor of life expectancy. With an R^2 of 0.229 this shows that education contributed 2% to life expectancy in the five countries. A t-value of all value of all five countries shows that none was significant in the use of education as a predictor of life expectancy. Although, human capital theory suggest that attaining higher levels of education leads to more and better employment opportunities, greater economic resources, access to social network and life styles that reduce risk taking behavior and better diets, all of which are associated with better health outcomes, this present study has neither accepted nor disprove this. The present study supports the study of Walton & Takeuchi (2008) who reported that despite the well-established relationship between educational attainment and physical health status, it is not entirely evident that the association is consistent across diverse racial and ethnic groups.

The influence of health as a multi-variety factor in a nation health was addressed by Beidler (2007). This author stated that health of the poor will often draws down the scale of health of the rich. Citing US as an example Beidler (2007) stated that it is the health status of the poorest groups that leads to the United States moderate health status despite the huge amount of money spent on health of its people.

The findings of this study support this tenet in that Nigeria and Ghana with a health budget allocation of 1% and 7% respectively the prediction of HIV/AIDS prevalence on life expectancy is significant. Australia with 15%, United State of America 14.1%, and United Kingdom 15% of their budget on health expenditure not only have a higher life expectancy but HIV/AIDS prevalence cannot be used to predict their life expectancy. Therefore African countries (Ghana and Nigeria) in this study must adopt the Africa Public health Alliance and the “15 percent now! a campaign which was launched on the international human right day on 10th December 2006. The call was to show the world that public health for Africa is a right and an important developmental issue across Africa (Davidamuk 2008).

Implication for Health Promotion

The absence of statistics in many African countries is both a symptom and a cause of underdevelopment. Improvement of statistical systems should be seen as a priory by developing countries. Statistics is needed in the assessment of the magnitude of the developmental issues. Scaling up of interventions becomes difficult and resources might be allocated away from more pressing issues. Furthermore without adequate statistics, assessment of the effectiveness of various programmes after implementation becomes difficult.

The absence of adequate statistics has immediate implications for policymakers. The quality of social statistics (compiled by both governmental and international agencies) in countries such as Nigeria is wanting. The low quality of statistics results in adverse outcomes, such as underfunding and poor monitoring of many development programmes. The premise is that without reliable information, government officials who allocate resources for health budgets in such countries are essentially working in the dark.

Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala and Philip Osafo-Kwaako (2007) questioned the low life-expectancy (at birth) of about 47 years in Nigeria. These authors argued that this is an underestimate based on the empirical reality. Casual empiricism based on observations in various parts of Nigeria suggests that life expectancy tends to be a few years higher, particularly given Nigeria's low and declining HIV/AIDS prevalence rates compared with other African countries. Governments and donor agencies must view reliable data as an important tool in the development process, and must invest both financial and human resources in strengthening their statistical systems.

There is therefore the need for the Nigerian government to raise health expenditure to the 15% of the budget as was agreed at the various summits (the 15% now in Abuja, in Egypt, 7th Anniversary of the African Union) HIV/AIDS campaigns must be intensified and sustained, while Tuberculosis, malaria, child mortality, and maternal mortality must be seen as collective and individual issue.

Nigerian government should make more effort at increasing school enrollment at the primary and secondary levels. This must be followed with employment for all programmes so as to raise the living standard of the people. Industrialization and urbanization will make meaning only if urban immigrants are provided with job. The rural areas must be made attractive with the provision of employment, essential services such as functional electricity, water and security of life and property. This comprehensive approach to health status will increase life expectancy among Nigeria. Nigerian must reduce the disparity between the poor and the rich, the educated and the uneducated, the male and the female the rural and urban areas. All these integrated is what this researcher refer to as health promotion.

Limitation

The lack of reliable and good-quality statistics assessing changes in health indicators in many African countries is a major limitation in this comparative study. Locating health statistics in Ghana and Nigeria has been more problematic than that of US and UK. The lack of health statistics ranges from poor systems for civil registration to poor data on immunization and child mortality rates. Data collecting efforts therefore vary considerably around the world and comparative data are not always available.

CONCLUSION

This research, using secondary data has revealed that while developing countries could predict their life expectancy through HIV/AIDS infestation (Nigeria and Ghana), the same does not apply to developed countries like Australia, United Kingdom and United States of America. Education cannot be used to predict life expectancy in all the five countries studied (Australia, United Kingdom, United States of America, Nigeria and Ghana). As noted earlier, in developing countries, a large portion of health fund is dependent upon external or foreign aid. As expensive as it may seem, health systems are an investment in people. Healthier people can contribute to the economy and society more easily, which for poorer countries is even more essential. But the structure of the health system, as well as spending, needs to be appropriate and take into account local conditions and constraints. Despite improvements over time, the challenge remains enormous. The WHO and others non-governmental agencies must continually identify areas where health provision can be far more cost effective than is currently provided, even with severe budget constraints. This is the hope for a healthier future. Nigeria government should increase her health expenditure to meet the 15% of national budget. HIV/AIDS campaigns should be intensified and sustained so as to drastically reduce the present rate of prevalence. Nigeria government at every level should adopt integrated approach to enhance the health status of her citizens, so as to increase her life expectancy

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